

Establishing an emotionally durable relationship between product and consumer

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Abstract

This paper firstly considers the challenges and opportunities facing designers who attempt to emotionally connect with consumers through their products design. Secondly, it describes an experiment which captured six participants' emotional responses to the aesthetic design of a number of lighting products. Thirdly, the results of the experiment are discussed with respect to how emotion capture could be introduced as a design education tool to assist with the design process as a whole, and in particular, the concept selection process.

Conference theme: Emotion in Design Education

Keywords: Design education, product, emotion, concept selection, eye tracker, design classic, emotionally durable design.

Introduction

In today's highly competitive consumer market it has become increasingly difficult for organisations to gain competitive advantage on the basis of price, quality and technology (Jordan, 2000). Aesthetic design has therefore become a key factor in product differentiation. Furthermore, previous studies have identified that consumer's emotional responses to products have a considerable influence on purchase decisions (Desmet, 2004). This knowledge has driven organisations to challenge designers to manipulate the emotional impact of their products through design. However, due to the idiosyncratic nature of emotion phenomena designers are often timorous, or reluctant, to confront this challenge. Over the last twenty years a number of tools and methods have been developed to assist the integration of affective aspects such as emotions and consumer perceptions into the product development lifecycle. This study will consider if emotion capture tools could be beneficial as a design education tool to assist the design process as a whole, and in particular, the concept selection process. The study will focus on emotions elicited by design classics (Phaidon, 2006) to determine if there are any specific emotions evoked by design classics. This is an important area to consider as emotional design is often associated with a consumer's irrational desire to purchase a product which does not function properly or for which they have no use (Norman, 2005). However, in today's climate of environmental concern, a more responsible use of emotional impact would be to design products that consumers could have a sustainable emotional relationship with. This could potentially reduce the need for consumers to be constantly looking to replace their perfectly functioning products. Furthermore, introducing emotional design to students as a way to achieve enhanced product sustainability provides a clear rationale for students to understand.

Design and Emotion

The difficulty designers face when attempting to influence or control the emotions elicited by products stems from the three key issues surrounding product related emotions. Firstly, emotions are personal and therefore two individuals could experience different emotions to the same product. Secondly, products can elicit more than one emotion and thirdly, products can elicit all types of emotion (Desmet 2002). These issues demonstrate the complexity of product related emotions and heighten a designer's apprehension in attempting to manipulate the emotions a product could evoke. However, emotion theorists such as Lazarus (1991) suggest that there are universal conditions that underlie and evoke an emotion and that each distinct emotion is brought about by a unique pattern of eliciting conditions. This means that although

consumers may experience different emotions from one another towards a product, the emotions that they do experience result from a universal pattern of eliciting conditions.

Methodology

The purpose of this study was to identify any features, characteristics or properties of emotional product durability by examining a range of products that represent timeless design. Ten lighting products were selected from Phaidon design classics (Phaidon, 2006). Phaidon design classics were selected by a large community of design experts including academics, critics, historians, curators, journalists, designers and architects to represent Phaidon's definition of design classic "Industrially manufactured objects of aesthetic value and timeless quality."

In order to represent timeless design the lighting products were selected based on the criteria that they have remained aesthetically unchanged since their conception and are still currently available to purchase. The lights selected were designed between 1903- 2002 and represent different time periods within this time frame. The lighting products selected are shown in Figure 1. The details of each of the products can be found below:

- 1. Fortuny Moda Lamp, designed in 1903 by Mariano Fortuny Y Madrazo available from Pallucco Italia*
- 2. MT8 Table Lamp, designed in 1924 by Wilhelm Wagenfeld, available from Tecnolumen*
- 3. Anglepoise, designed in 1935 by George Cardwardine, available from Anglepoise*
- 4. Three-legged cylinder lamp, designed in 1944 by Isamu Noguchi, available from Vitra design museum*
- 5. Tubino, designed by Achille Castiglioni in 1948, currently produced by Habitat.*
- 6. Moon Lamp, designed by Verner Panton in 1960, available from Vitra design museum*
- 7. Arco, designed by Achille Castiglioni in 1962, available from Flos*
- 8. Tizio, designed by Richard Sapper in 1971, available from Artemide*
- 9. Ara, designed by Phillippe Starck in 1988, available from Flos*
- 10. Radom Light, designed by Bertian Pot in 2002, available from Moooi*

Figure1: Ten lighting products selected from Phaidon Design Classics for use in the study (Phaidon 2006)

The study used an eye tracker, characters, words and interviews to capture the emotional responses of the participants toward the products. The characters used were those developed by Desmet for the PrEmo tool (Desmet, 2002). The characters represent seven positive emotions and seven negative emotions and can be seen together with their related emotion descriptive words in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Desmet's PrEmo characters and related descriptive words (Desmet 2002)

Six final year male product design students volunteered to participate in the experiment which involved three stages.

Stage One – Eye Tracker

Stage one involved the participants viewing images of the ten lighting products on a computer screen. Each participant viewed the images in the same order. An eye tracker was used to capture how each participant viewed each product, identifying products and features that each of the participants spent most time looking at.

Stage Two – Emotional words and characters

Participants were first asked to assign one, more than one or none of Desmets 14 characters, which they felt best represented how the product made them feel. Participants had no prior knowledge of Desmets characters. Participants were also asked to select words that they felt best represented how the product made them feel. The participants were not made aware that the words corresponded to the characters.

Stage Three - Interview

Stage three took the form of a 20 minute structured interview. Participants were asked to discuss each of the lighting products and what they liked or disliked about each of them. They were then asked to discuss the characters and words that they had assigned to each product. Participants were also asked about their current design projects and if they had ever considered the emotional impact of their designs before. They were asked if they thought designers could manipulate the emotions that their designs evoked and if they found any of the tools used in the experiment useful.

Results

Emotion descriptive words

Figure 3 shows the results of the emotion descriptive words which participants choose to represent how each of the products made them feel. Out of the 14 emotion descriptive words available to choose from, only 12 were selected. The two words which were not selected by any participant were indignant and unpleasant surprise. The words which were selected the most often were admire, dissatisfaction and inspired. Product number 8 was assigned with seven positive emotion words and zero negative words. When the number of positive and negative words were tallied, product numbers 1, 4, 7 and 9 resulted in a negative or zero total.

Words	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Positive emotions	Inspired Fascination	Admire Admire Satisfied	Inspired Admire Amused Desire	Inspired Satisfied Satisfied	Admire Admire Admire Admire Satisfied	Inspired Inspired Fascination Fascination	Admire Satisfied	Inspired Inspired Admire Desire PI-Surprise Fascination Fascination	Inspired Desire Fascination	Inspired Admire Amused Desire
+ ve	+2	+3	+4	+3	+5	+4	+2	+7	+3	+4
Negative Emotions	Bored Dissatisfied	Bored Dissatisfied	Bored Disgusted	Bored Dissatisfied Disgusted Disappointed	Bored Dissatisfied	Disappointed Disappointed	Disappointed Dissatisfied Disgusted		Disappointed Dissatisfied Disgusted	contempt
- ve	-2	-2	-2	-4	-2	-2	-3	0	-3	-1
Sum	0	+1	+2	-1	+3	+2	-1	+7	0	+3

Figure 3: Results of selected emotion descriptive words

Emotion descriptive characters

Figure 4 shows the results of the corresponding words relating to the characters which participants choose to represent how each of the products made them feel. All 14 of the characters were selected at least once. The most popular characters selected were satisfaction and fascination. The characters selected the least were desire, pleasant surprise, dissatisfaction and unpleasant surprise. Product number 8 was assigned with six positive emotion characters and zero negative characters. Product number 9 was assigned five negative emotion characters and only one positive emotion character. When the number of positive and negative characters were tallied, product number 8 resulted in the highest value and product number 9 the lowest.

Characters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Positive emotions	Admire Admire Fascination	Satisfied Satisfied	Satisfied Satisfied	Inspired Satisfied Fascinated	Admire PI-Surprise Satisfied	Amused Amused Fascination Fascination	Inspired Satisfied	Satisfied Satisfied Desire Fascination Fascination Fascination	Satisfied	Inspired Admire Satisfied
+ ve	+3	+2	+2	+3	+3	+4	+2	+6	+1	+3
Negative Emotions	Bored Bored Contempt	Contempt Contempt Disgusted	Bored Disgusted	Bored Dissatisfied	Bored Bored	Indignant	Disappointed Disappointed Disappointed		Disappointed Dissatisfied Disgusted Indignant Unp-surprise	Disappointed
- ve	-3	-3	-2	-2	-2	-1	-3	0	-5	-1
Sum	0	-1	0	+1	+1	+3	-1	+6	-4	+2

Figure 4: Results of corresponding words relating to selected emotion characters

Product eliciting the most positive emotions

Table 1 shows the participants responses to product number 8 in more detail. The majority of the participant responses when interviewed highlighted that they were intrigued by how the product worked and that they wanted to touch it and play with it. The technical aspects and the simple clutter-free design were also mentioned. The most common emotion elicited was fascination. Participants were fascinated by how the product worked and balanced. This was verified by the eye tracker results which showed that all of the participants focused on the joints and weights.

		Product Name: Tizio Designed: 1972 Designer: Richard Sapper	
Participant	Eye Tracker	Emotions	Comments
1		W - Satisfied C - Inspired	Mechanical, Functional, Clutter free, Not traditional
2		W -Fascination C - Desire	Interesting, Looks modern but probably older. Want to know more about it, how it works, want to touch it
3		W - Admire W - Pl Surprise C - Satisfied C - Fascination	Intrigued by how it works, likes the counterbalance action. Enjoys the clean lines and the sharp angles.
4		W- Fascination C - Fascination	Interested by the way it is weighted and balanced. Wants to find out how it moves. Wants to interact with it.
5		W - Inspired C - Fascination	Wants to find out how it works, wants to touch it and play with it. Loves how it balances.
6		W - Admire C - Satisfied	Looks technical and precise but also quite simple. Would really like to own one. Looks like one small change to the design would make it not work.

Table 1: Results for the product evoking the most positive emotions (Product 8) (Phaidon 2006) (W=Words, C=Characters)

Product eliciting the most negative emotions

Table 2 shows the responses to product number 9 in more detail. Five of the six participants disliked the product, the majority of whom felt that the head and the base did not work well together. The eye tracker results show that participants focused primarily on the head which was the area that most participants found particularly dissatisfying. Two of the participants questioned the designers thinking.

		Product Name: Ara Designed: 1988 Designer: Phillippe Starck	
Participant	Eye tracker	Emotions	Comments
1		W - C - Indignant	Ultra masculine, Speed, velocity, Ego driven design. Almost feel contempt for the masculine statement that it makes
2		W - Admire W - Desire W - Fascination C - Satisfied	Looks precious, want to know why its sharp, want to know more about it
3		W - Dissatisfied C - Disgusted	Top and the base don't work together at all. The bottom is very basic and the top part more fluid. Really don't like it.
4		W -Disappointed C - Disappointed	It looks odd, the curve looks like it should be going the other way. The top and the bottom don't match at all. If I saw it in a shop I would question it.
5		W -Disappointed C - Unp Surprise	Don't like it at all, it makes me cringe and feel embarrassed. It looks sharp like a knife and you would never want to touch it.
6		W - Disgusted C - Dissatisfied	Don't like it at all. It looks like a bone or a horn or a stick. Don't know what the designer was thinking. It looks wrong.

Table 2 Results from the product eliciting most negative (Product 9) (Pahidon 2006) (W=Words, C=Characters)

Interview results

All of the participants agreed that designers could manipulate the emotions elicited by a products design but that it was a difficult task often achieved through a subtle selection of texture, material and finish. Two of the participants said that they had considered the emotional impact of their designs and that they wanted to evoke intrigue and desire however none of the participants had ever used any tools or methods to assist with designing for emotion or to measure the emotions elicited by their designs. All of the participants agreed that the tools used in the experiment would be useful in the product development process agreeing that they would be particularly useful to aid concept selection. Four of the six participants thought that the eye

tracker would be particularly useful to identify key product features of interest. Two of the participants felt that whilst the eye tracker was useful it needed to be backed up by some other tool as the interest could be positive or negative. There were mixed views as to whether the words or characters were easier to select. One participant thought that providing the words was a bit suggestive and that he often changed how he felt about the products to suit the available words. One participant thought that the characters were easier to choose than the words but also felt that people's interpretation of the characters emotions would probably vary considerably. One participant expressed particular dislike for the characters claiming that he could not relate to the characters at all and felt all of the expressions were too exaggerated for him to feel comfortable selecting them.

Discussion

All of the lighting products used in the study were selected from Phaidon design classics (Phaidon 2006) and were awarded the title of design classic due to their durability in the market and timeless quality. These products were selected to represent emotionally durable products. The product evoking the most positive emotions elicited fascination, inspiration and satisfaction however more research is required to assess whether these are representative emotions elicited by design classics.

As organisations continue to challenge designers to manipulate the emotions elicited by products it is increasingly important that design students are exposed to the challenge. The students all found the eye tracker very interesting although it provided no indication as to whether the participant's interest in a particular product or feature was positive or negative. For example, the eye tracker identified interest in the features participants were most fascinated by in product number 8 but also identified interest in the feature that participants were most dissatisfied with in product number 9. Eye tracking technology would therefore need to be used in conjunction with another tool to provide some context for the interest.

Some students responded better to selecting words to express how the products made them feel whilst others responded better to the characters. Although both the characters and the words produced similar results in terms of positive and negative responses, the responses did vary and there were few occasions when participants selected the correct corresponding words and characters. Further investigation of these tools and other developed tools and methods is required to establish the most appropriate method for design education.

All of the participants expressed an interest in designing for emotion but none had any real understanding of how to tackle it or measure it which implies that more education in this area is required. The interview stage proved really valuable by encouraging the students to use vocabulary they would not normally associate with design and rationalise how and why they felt about each product. This type of discussion is a critical foundation for design and emotion understanding.

Further Work

The experiment required the participants to select words and characters that they felt best represented how each of the products made them feel. However, emotions are primarily unconscious and it could be argued that the participants would be unable to convey real emotions as the tasks they were asked to complete required some form of cognitive appraisal. Furthermore, the eye tracking results captured the participants gaze and recorded features that participants spent most time looking at, although without further evidence the areas attracting the most visual attention cannot be attributed to the emotions evoked. Further work must be carried out to capture the emotions experienced without involving any cognitive appraisal. The next stage of this research will include automatic facial expression classification in order to automatically detect and analyse human facial expressions.

The association between facial expressions and emotions is well established and Ekman (1999) argues that facial expressions can be directly related to the changes in the physiology of emotion and are universal. The tool which will be used is the “Noldus facereader” (Noldus 2008) which will automatically recognize specific properties of facial expressions and interpret them to the six fundamental human emotions, happy, sad, angry, surprised, scared, disgusted and neutral. The participants for of the next experiment will be less design conscious in an attempt to represent the average consumer and eliminate any biases that perhaps design students could have toward design classics. Further research is also required to establish any differences between emotional responses to product appearance and those to product consumption. Also, assessing the change of emotions over a period of time, again considering appearance only and comparing it with product usage, could prove valuable for emotional product durability.

References

- Desmet, P.M.A. (2002). "Designing Emotions." Doctoral thesis. TU-Delft.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2004). "From disgust to desire: How products elicit emotions". Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Design & Emotion, pp. 8-12
- Ekman, P. (1999) "Facial Expressions". In T. Dalgleish and T. Power (Ed.). The Handbook of Cognition and Emotion, pp. 301-320
- Jordan, P.W. (2000) "Designing pleasurable products, an introduction to the new human factors.
- Lazarus, R.S., (1991), "*Emotion and adaptation*"
- Noldus. (2008). Retrieved July 09,2008 from <http://www.noldus.com>
- Phaidon Press Limited (2006) "Phaidon Design Classics Volume 1-3"